

Physical Layer Security in Cognitive Vehicular Networks

Sagar Kavaiya, Dhaval K. Patel, *Member, IEEE*, Zhiguo Ding, *Fellow, IEEE*,
Yong Liang Guan, *Senior Member, IEEE*, Sumei Sun, *Fellow, IEEE*

Abstract

In contrast with the traditional cryptography, physical layer security has attracted the attention of many researchers having aim at reinforcing the security of communication systems. As far as vehicular communication is concerned, it is challenging to maintain secure and reliable communication between the connected vehicles due to the density, mobility, and dynamic network topology. This paper considers a vehicle to infrastructure communication in which a legitimately fixed transmitter equipped with a single antenna transmits a confidential message to a legitimate mobile receiver equipped with multiple antennas in the presence of a passive mobile eavesdropper. In such a single input multiple output wireless system, the receiver performs the maximal ratio combining technique assuming constant vehicle speed. We assume that the antennas are closely spaced and depending upon the imperfect channel state information (CSI), we derive the closed-form expressions for the average outage probability, secrecy outage probability, and average secrecy outage rate over the uniform, exponential, and arbitrary correlated Nakagami- m channels for dual antenna branches. In order to gain insight we also perform the high SNR asymptotic analysis of the outage probability and secrecy outage probability. Simulations are conducted to validate the accuracy of our derived analytic expressions. The computation error analysis is carried out to provide the suitability of the correlation type at the legitimate receiver side. Our findings suggest that the performance of the case with exponential channel correlation is better than those for the uniform and arbitrary. Numerical results show the joint effect of vehicle mobility and the antenna correlation on secrecy performance. Moreover, we also observed that the imperfect knowledge of the CSI degrades the security of the confidential messages severely under the effect of mobility.

Manuscript received June 04, 2020, revised October 10, 2020. Authors would like to thank financial support received from DST-ASEAN (grant ref. IMRC/AISTDF/RD/P-09/2017). Sagar Kavaiya and Dhaval K Patel are with School of Engineering and Applied Science Ahmedabad University, India. (Email:sagar.k@ahduni.edu.in, dhaval.patel@ahduni.edu.in).

Z. Ding is with the School of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, The University of Manchester, Manchester M13 9PL, United Kingdom (e-mail: zhiguo.ding@manchester.ac.uk)

Yong Liang Guan is with School of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Nanyang Technological University (NTU), Singapore. (Email:eylguan@ntu.edu.sg).

Sumei Sun is with Institute of Infocomm Research, Singapore. (Email:sunsm@i2r.a-star.edu.sg).

Index Terms

V2I Communications, Physical Layer Security, inter-antenna correlation, Nakagami- m channel, secrecy outage probability, outage probability

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background

Secure communications over wireless channels at the physical layer has attracted great research attention. Traditionally, security was regarded as an independent issue beyond the physical layer and was well studied through designing and implementing cryptographic algorithms. Still, in recent years, wireless researchers have wanted a replacement of the security paradigm with traditional security which is termed as physical layer security (PLS). Unlike the traditional scientific discipline approach, which ignores the impact of the wireless medium, PLS exploits the necessary characteristics of the wireless channel, like attenuation, interference, and noise, for raising the communication security against eavesdropping attacks. In contrast with the established application of computational security, many results from scientific theory [1], signal processing, and cryptography recommends that there is much security to be gained by considering the imperfections of the physical layer when coming up with security systems. Moreover, when the user mobility is concerned, it is challenging to provide security at the physical layer [1].

B. Literature Review

The secret key management in an opportunistic way is suggested for wireless networks and the condition for perfect secret communication between legitimate transmitter and receiver has been provided in [2]. As a pioneer work, Shannon proposed a fundamental mathematical structure of secrecy systems in terms of stochastic processes in which a discrete sequence of symbols is produced as a system of probabilities [3]. Authors in [4] have provided various approaches for PLS with comparison in which secret channel capacity and computational complexity were compared. Assuming the perfect (error-free) transmission, the trade-off between transmission rate and the equivocation has been proposed under the wiretap channel and the possibility of the secrecy capacity at particular secrecy rate has been provided [5].

The above works are mainly for the single antenna systems, but in multi-antenna systems, demonstration of the perfect secrecy under the artificial noise has been covered in [6]. The multiple antennas are used to generate artificial noise in such a way that there is a degradation in eavesdropper's channel. Furthermore, for a transmitter, having a multiple antenna, the generation of artificial noise using a relay is provided to achieve secrecy in communication systems [6]. A detailed survey has been given, including the state-of-art for non cognitive radio enabled vehicle

to vehicle communications. [7].

For cognitive radio (CR) systems, the issues related to security are highlighted in [8]. Securing communications in cognitive radio networks with the analysis of secrecy capacity is covered and most of the issues are highlighted like eavesdropping, malicious user detection in the jamming attack, learning attack in [9]–[12]. For a more dynamic scenario, the assumption of imperfect channel state condition is considered for multiple input single output wireless systems under transmit antenna selection. The closed-form expression with proper assumptions related to channel conditions for outage probability was derived, concluding that diversity gain can not be realized under imperfect channel conditions [13]. For CR cellular wireless communication systems, authors in [14], proposed an analytical model to obtain secrecy outage probability (SOP) for single input multiple output (SIMO) system under Nakagami- m fading channel. Furthermore, PLS for multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) systems has been analyzed considering Nakagami- m fading under optimal, sub-optimal, and transmit antenna selection scheme [15]. Multi-user MIMO systems considering spatial correlation among the antennas with receive antenna selection are studied to provide ergodic capacity assuming imperfect channel conditions. Capacity expressions are also derived in terms of channel mean square error [16].

Furthermore, several works have been done over the Rayleigh fading like [17], secrecy capacity over double Rayleigh fading channels were derived and analyzed. The obtained results can be used for the secrecy capacity analysis for vehicle to vehicle (V2V) and machine to machine communications as well as for the keyhole channels [17]. Investigations of average secrecy capacity and secrecy outage for both independent and correlated log normal fading channels and composite fading channels are carried out in [18]. In [19], authors have considered the diversity in transmission schemes and shows the impact of having multiple transmit antennas on secrecy rate. Closed form expressions of secrecy outage probability are derived. Moreover, for CR networks, the extension of [5] has been provided by the authors in [20] by considering SIMO system assuming colored additive white Gaussian noise. In [21], an assumption of imperfect channel state information was adopted for static relay based networks.

In [22], authors have provided an overview of the signal processing techniques to enhance PLS. While data transmission beam forming in secrecy and preceding schemes are used to make the signal weak at eavesdropper side. To confuse the steady and passive eavesdropper artificial noise has been added to the eavesdropper's link with and without precoding techniques [23]. In [24], authors have elaborated challenges and opportunities regarding the vehicular communication in the context of PLS by highlighting the analytical approach for study. Based on high demands in quality of service, ultra low latency and high reliability for the vehicular networks is taken

into consideration. Furthermore, the problem of multi antenna transmission over small scale fading under perfect secrecy for CR networks is highlighted for static users and authors have illustrated the algorithms to achieve the maximum secrecy [25]. The impact of mobility over random way point mobility model has been studied in [26] for PLS. Author provides the trade off between secrecy improvement and transmit outage probability. The existing works in [27]–[29] focus on the secrecy performance for vehicular networks for single antenna systems. The works carried out in [30]–[34] focused on secrecy performance of SIMO systems over correlated k - μ fading, unmanned arial vehicle assisted in CR networks, UAV over randomly located eavesdroppers, reconfigurable intelligent surfaces aided wireless systems, correlated α - μ fading, and with multiple eavesdroppers, respectively.

In contrast to the all above works, there are some limitations of the existing literature, including single antenna systems, static users and perfect channel knowledge. In order to consider the realistic vehicular scenario, the small scale fading conditions under the impact of antenna correlations is one of the main issues through which the privacy of the current systems can be compromised. Moreover, when the channel knowledge is considered as imperfect, the system performance can be degraded which is very intuitive. However, to gain insight in the privacy of such considered systems, the quantification of the performance metric is done by findings the closed form expressions of secrecy outage probability (SOP) and outage probability (OP) which is new in the literature. Therefore, our aim is to provide the comprehensive set of closed-form expressions which helps to derive an inference of the privacy of the vehicular networks.

C. Motivation and Contributions

From the existing literature, it can be noticed that few works have been reported in context of securing communications for vehicular networks. Under the mobility constraint, the sensing performance is evaluated for cognitive radio networks. Miss detection and false alarm probabilities are derived assuming Nakagami- m , Nakagami- q , κ - μ , and η - μ channels [35] but few literature for securing communications at the physical layer is reported under the mobility constraint over small scale fading channels. Furthermore, to the best of author’s knowledge no work exists in literature which considers the realistic vehicular scenario in which perfect secrecy is achieved while assuming imperfect knowledge of channel state information. In addition, based on the spacing between multiple antennas, the correlation occurs which can significantly affects the system performance in terms of outage situations. The main contributions of our work are as follows:

- 1) Probability distribution function (PDF) of received signal-to-noise ratio (SNR): We obtained the statistical knowledge of the received SNR over uniformly, exponentially and

arbitrarily correlated Nakagami- m channel with imperfect CSI for dual antenna branches. By considering the initial location of the legitimate receiver, we obtained the PDF of received SNR under the impact of mobility. The obtained PDF is useful to derive the closed form expressions of outage probability and secrecy outage probability.

- 2) Average outage probability: It is advantageous to have a knowledge regarding an information rate at which the eavesdropping is possible and when the user is mobile, to obtain the knowledge about the outage conditions becomes more challenging. So that, as a solution, we derive an exact closed-form expression for outage probability for uniformly, exponentially and arbitrarily correlated dual antenna receivers assuming maximal ratio combining diversity and imperfect channel condition under Nakagami- m fading. The benefit of our approximation will lead toward the signal to noise (SNR) requirement at the legitimate receiver side to achieve outage as less as possible. Moreover when we assume the branch as independent and identically distributed (*i.i.d*) or uncorrelated the derived expressions are reduced as per [14].
- 3) Secrecy outage probability: Aiming that to achieve perfect secrecy in presence of passive and mobile eavesdropper located in network, we provide Secrecy Outage Probability (SOP) analysis under correlated Nakagami- m fading conditions. The SOP is derived by considering uniform, exponential and arbitrary correlation.
- 4) Asymptotic analysis of outage probability and secrecy outage probability: In order to gain insight on the secrecy performance at high SNR at the legitimate receiver, the asymptotic analysis is carried out over correlated Nakagami- m fading conditions.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the complete system model with position of legitimate transmitter and eavesdropper as shown in Figure 1. In Section III analysis of the average outage probability and secrecy outage probability is carried out for uniform correlation. Section IV describes the analysis of outage and secrecy probability for exponential correlation. Section V gives closed form expressions for average outage and secrecy for arbitrary correlation. Section VI provides the complete information on numerical results. Section VII provides the conclusion of carried research followed by the references.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Consider the urban vehicular scenario suggested in Fig 1. P is a primary user. The static legitimate transmitter is denoted by S . Car (R) is a secondary user (SU) equipped with a legitimate receiver which is allowed to receive an information after the resource allocation has been provided in the cognitive radio based network. Here car (E) performs a role of an

Fig. 1: Urban Vehicular to Infrastructure (V2I) and Vehicular to Vehicular (V2V) scenario

passive eavesdropper which is a part of the network. The length of the road $a = 4km$, legitimate transmitter's protection range $R' = 1km$. The distance between the nearest side of road to the legitimate transmitter (s) is $d'' = 400m$, The width of the road $b = 30m$. The fading links are following a dynamic Nakagami- m channel with all necessary assumption like Doppler shift and time varying quantity. In this scenario, every vehicles are having dual antennas in which the correlation parameter is modeled by constant, exponential and arbitrary correlation among them. The channel state information (CSI) is considered to be imperfect. The receiver performs the maximal ratio combining (MRC) method among the available copies of transmitted signal. Assuming that the vehicle is moving with the constant speed, the combination of all parameters are creating a more realistic scenario in which the received signal vector at passive eavesdropper builds a SIMO system in which the received signal at eavesdropper and receiver are given as

$$r_k(t) = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{t})s(t) + n(t), \quad (1)$$

Here $k \in \{E, R\}$, $h(t)$ is a time varying channel coefficient vector which is correlated Nakagami- m under MRC diversity over the imperfect channel condition. s is the transmitted symbol, n is the complex hardware additive white Gaussian noise, while t denotes the time constraint which implies the channel is time varying or the received signal varies with respect to mobility of the vehicle. Under the imperfect channel condition h_x can be given as per [14]:

$$h_x(t) = \sqrt{\psi}h_k(t) + \sqrt{1 - \psi^2}n_k, \quad (2)$$

where ψ is the imperfectness parameter that controls the channel, h_k is the fading co-efficient between single antenna transmitter and k^{th} antenna receiver, n_k is the estimation error which is complex in nature or circularly symmetric noise. Note that, the estimated channel coefficient is independent of n_k . While considering the effect of path loss and small scale fading, the h_k is further expressed as a function of distance between legitimate transmitter and eavesdropper as follows:

$$h_k(t) = \frac{g_x}{\sqrt{1 + d_X^\alpha}}, \quad (3)$$

where α denotes the path loss exponent, g_x is the channel gain over various correlation schemes like equal, exponential and arbitrary following Nakagami- m distribution. The simplest characterization of a mobile radio channel is done in terms of the average attenuation as a function of the distance between the transmitter and the receiver. This is referred to as path loss and is due to the free-space propagation losses and effects like absorption and diffraction, among others. Path loss increases with distance, normally following a power law, d^ζ , where ζ is called the path loss exponent. Furthermore, for vehicular communications Nakagami- m channel model is considered as a general and suitable model for small scale variation. Even for a fixed distance, the received signal level fluctuates when moving on a circle around the transmitter. These fluctuations are due to the small-scale changes in the phase/ amplitude of the propagation paths from the transmitter to the receiver, which are analyzed in our work by considering the Nakagami- m fading model. d_X is the distribution of distance. Furthermore, the total effective SNR over MRC branches is given as [36]:

$$\gamma_k = \frac{E_s}{N_0} \sum_{l=1}^L |h_l|^2, \quad (4)$$

where, E_s is the signal power and h_l is the amplitude coefficient of l^{th} branch. N_0 is the power of the additive white Gaussian noise. The probability of outage is defined as the probability that the received instantaneous SNR γ falls below a threshold γ_{th} . We define the notation γ_E , γ_R for the SNRs at the eavesdropper and legitimate receiver side, respectively. The secrecy outage probability is defined as the probability when the difference between capacities of the main and eavesdropper's channel is less than a certain code rate of R_s . Here, in our analysis, we assume the dual branches with uniform, exponential, and arbitrarily correlation, then we provide the closed-form expressions in upcoming sections.

III. SECRECY PERFORMANCE OVER UNIFORMLY CORRELATED NAKAGAMI- m FADING CHANNELS

In this section, we focus on the derivation of a received SNR to evaluate the outage and secrecy performance of a mobile receiver over imperfect CSI. PDF of uniformly correlated Nakagami- m fading channel for dual branches is expressed as [36]:

$$f_X(x) = \frac{x^{\frac{mL^2}{r}-1} \exp\left(\frac{-Lmx}{r\gamma_1}\right)}{x\left(\frac{mL^2}{r}\right)\left(\frac{r\gamma_1}{Lm}\right)^{\frac{mL^2}{r}}}, \quad (5)$$

where $r = 2 + \frac{2\rho}{1-\rho} \left(2 - \frac{1-\rho^L}{1-\rho}\right)$, ρ is uniform correlation coefficient. Under the vehicle mobility, the channel gain can be expressed as [37]:

$$h_X(t) = \frac{f_X(x)}{\sqrt{1+d_x^\alpha}}, \quad (6)$$

where $f_X(x)$ is the distribution of uniform correlated Nakagami- m channel. The denominator term is relabeled as $f_Y(y)$ which is the distribution of distance. The PDF of vehicle mobility is expressed as [38]:

$$f_Y(y) = \frac{d}{4ab} \left[\pi + 2\arcsin\left(\frac{2(y^2 - (d'')^2)}{y^2}\right) - 1 \right]. \quad (7)$$

The cumulative distribution function (CDF) of received SNR for uniformly correlated Nakagami- m fading can be calculated as:

$$F_Z(z) = \int_0^\infty \int_{-\infty}^{yz} f_{XY}(x, y) dx dy. \quad (8)$$

By substituting (5) and (7) in (8) the CDF can be written as:

$$F_Z(z) = \int_0^\infty \int_{-\infty}^{yz} \frac{x^{\frac{mL^2}{r}-1} \exp\left(\frac{-Lmx}{r\gamma_1}\right)}{x\left(\frac{mL^2}{r}\right)\left(\frac{r\gamma_1}{Lm}\right)^{\frac{mL^2}{r}}} \times \frac{d}{4ab} \left[\pi + 2\arcsin\left(\frac{2(y^2 - (b-s)^2)}{y^2}\right) - 1 \right] dx dy. \quad (9)$$

By integrating the equation (9) with the use of [39, Eq. (7.2.11)], we have a CDF for uniformly correlated Nakagami- m branches under vehicle mobility.

Lemma 3.1. *Under the impact of mobility, the CDF of received SNR for uniform correlation is obtained as the ratio of two distributions as:*

$$F_Z(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{T_k} A_k^n B_k^n \lambda_k^n z^m \cdot \frac{e^{z/ab}}{d}, \quad (10)$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the Gamma function, $A_k = \left(\frac{L}{\Gamma(m)}\right)$, $B_k = \left(\frac{\Gamma(m+d+r)L}{\Gamma(m)}\right)$, m is the Nakagami- m parameter, $T_k = m_k L$ and $\lambda_k = e^{T_k}$.

For proof, kindly refer to Appendix A ■

Corollary 3.1.1. *From the CDF experiencing the uniform correlation among the antenna branches, and from the definitions of PDF, by taking differentiation of (54), with the help of [39, Section 3], PDF for uniformly correlated Nakagami- m branches under vehicle mobility is expressed as follows:*

$$f_Z(z) = A_k B_k \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n m z^m \frac{e^{z/ab} (1/ab)}{d^2}. \quad (11)$$

Remark. *We note that, the PDF of received SNR is a function of initial distance of legitimate receiver. Finally from (9), the PDF of uniformly correlated Nakagami- m channels over imperfect CSI is obtained by differentiating with the help of [39] which is expressed as:*

$$f_Z(z) = \sqrt{\psi} A_k B_k \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n m z^m \frac{e^{z/ab} (1/ab)}{d^2} + \eta \sqrt{1-\psi}, \quad (12)$$

where ψ is the imperfect channel state controlling parameter and η is the estimation error.

A. Analysis of Outage Probability

Outage is stated as the probability that the received instantaneous SNR γ falls below a threshold γ_{th} . The outage probability for dual branch Nakagami - m over MRC in uniformly correlated fading channels can be written as:

$$P_{out} = Pr(\gamma \leq \gamma_{th}), \quad (13)$$

$$P_{out} = \int_{\gamma_{th}}^{\infty} f_Z(z) dz. \quad (14)$$

Substituting (12) in (14), The average probability of outage under vehicle mobility for a uniformly correlated Nakagami- m channels over imperfect CSI is expressed as

$$P_{out} = \int_{z_{th}}^{\infty} \sqrt{\psi} A_k B_k \times \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n m z^m \frac{e^{z/ab} (1/ab)}{d^2} + \eta \sqrt{1-\psi} dz. \quad (15)$$

Expanding the inner series term and integrating (15), we obtain the closed form expression of average outage probability using special integrals in [39, Eq.(8.2.2)]. The expression can be given as follows

$$P_{out} = 1 - e^{ab/z_{th}} \sum_{k=1}^{T_k} \sum_{n=0}^m \Gamma(e^{r-1} + z) + (\psi^3/2e^{-d} + \eta^2) C_k + D_k, \quad (16)$$

Eq (16) is the outage probability under uniform correlation. $C_k = \frac{z}{2abLm}$, $D_k = \frac{1-det(\Lambda)}{4d}$

B. Analysis of Secrecy Outage Probability

In this section, we analyze the secrecy outage probability at the passive eavesdropper side. However the legitimate transmitter does not have the CSI information of eavesdropper's channel and hence it has no choice to encode data under a constant code rate R_s . The instantaneous secrecy capacity is given by [14]

$$C_s(\gamma_E, \gamma_R) = \max \{ \ln(1 + \gamma_E) - \ln(1 + \gamma_R), 0 \}. \quad (17)$$

where γ_E and γ_R is the received SNR at eavesdropper and legitimate receiver respectively. The SOP is further expressed as

$$Pr \{ C_s(\gamma_R, \gamma_E) \leq R_s \}. \quad (18)$$

For the cognitive network, the transmitter power at S can be expressed as [14]:

$$P_s = \min \left(P_{max}, \frac{I_p}{X} \right), \quad (19)$$

where X is a Channel gain between primary transmitter and primary receiver, I_p is the interference power, P_{max} is the maximum transmitted power. The assumption of CR network remains same for all correlation schemes in the upcoming sections. Furthermore, this channel is considered as perfect hence to obtain the average outage. Finally, using (19), the SOP can be expressed as:

$$P_{sop} = \underbrace{Pr \{ C_s(\gamma_R, \gamma_E) \leq R_s, P_s = P_{max} \}}_{I_1} + \underbrace{Pr \left\{ C_s(\gamma_R, \gamma_E) \leq R_s, P_s = \frac{I_p}{X} \right\}}_{I_2}, \quad (20)$$

1) Derivation of I_1

When $P_s = P_{max}$, the term I_1 is given by

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= Pr \{C_s(\gamma_R, \gamma_E) \leq R_s, P_s = P_{max}\} \\ &= Pr \left\{ Z_R \leq \theta Z_E + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right\} Pr \left\{ x \leq \frac{I_P}{P_{max}} \right\} \\ &= \underbrace{\int_0^\infty F_{Z_D} \left(\theta z + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right) f_{Z_E}(z) dz}_{I_{11}} Pr \left\{ x \leq \frac{I_P}{P_{max}} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$Pr \left\{ x \leq \frac{I_P}{P_{max}} \right\}$ is given as $1/\Gamma(m)$. The derivation of I_{11} can be given as

$$\begin{aligned} I_{11} &= \int_0^\infty F_{Z_D} \left(\theta z + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right) f_{Z_E}(z) dz \\ &= \int_0^\infty A_k \sum B_k \sum_{n=0}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n z^m \frac{e^{z/ab}}{d} \times \left(\theta z + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right) \times \sqrt{\psi} A_k \sum B_k \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n m z^m \frac{e^{z/ab}(1/ab)}{d^2} \\ &\quad + \eta \sqrt{1 - \psi} dz. \end{aligned}$$

Note that the above integral does not converge for any fixed value of z . However, the integral can be solved by taking an appropriate identity from [39, Section 6.4]. FOn rewriting the above term, we have

$$I_{11} = \int_0^\infty A_k \sum B_k \sum_{n=0}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n z^m \frac{e^{z/ab}}{d} \times \left(\theta z + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right) \times \sqrt{\psi} A_k \sum B_k \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n m z^m \frac{e^{z/ab}(1/ab)}{d^2} dz.$$

The rest integral with the summation is given as

$$I_{11} = \int_0^\infty A_k \sum B_k \sum_{n=0}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n z^m \frac{e^{z/ab}}{d} \times \left(\theta z + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right) \times \eta \sqrt{1 - \psi} dz.$$

By keeping the constant outside the integral and further solving by using special integral [40, Eq 8.2.1]. We obtain:

$$I_{11} = A_R A_E \sum_{S_R} \sum_{S_E} \sum_{i=0}^{T_R} \sum_{j=1}^{T_E} \times \left(B_R B_E \lambda_R^i \lambda_E^j \frac{e^{ab}}{d} \right) \times \sum_{n=0}^{L_R} C \theta^n \binom{L_R}{n} \frac{\theta - 1}{\psi_R \alpha}^{1-n}. \quad (21)$$

Here $C = \left(L_E \Gamma \left(\frac{n+\psi}{\eta_D \theta} \right) \right)$, $\theta = e^{R_s}$, $A_R = \frac{2\rho_k}{2d^2+1}$, $B_R = \frac{1}{L_m}$, $A_E = B_E = 1/m$. Note that the SOP of legitimate receiver depends upon its channel conditions and as well as the number of antennas at eavesdropper side. The analytical expression (19) states that SOP is affected by the uniform correlation among the antennas.

2) Derivation of I_2

When the $P_S = \frac{I_P}{X}$, by using (14), we can obtain

$$I_2 = \int_{I_P/P_{Max}}^{\infty} H(x)f_X(x)dx. \quad (22)$$

where $H(x) = \int_0^{\infty} F_{Y_R}(\theta y + (\theta - 1)) f_{Y_E}(y)dy$

By solving above integral with the help of [39, Section 3] we have an additional term for the SOP. Here, the CDF in (9) is relabeled as F_{Y_R} and the PDF of it relabeled as f_{Y_E} .

$$I_2 = A_R A_E \sum_{i=0}^{T_R} \sum_{i=0}^{T_E} (B_R B_E \lambda_R \lambda_E \theta^n x^{L_E}). \quad (23)$$

Kindly refer Appendix A ■

C. Asymptotic Analysis of Secrecy Outage Probability

From the expression of SOP in (20), we can notice that for the considered case, only integrals I_{11} will be influenced. On rewriting I_1 , we have

$$\begin{aligned} I_{11, \infty} &= \int_0^{\infty} F_{Z_R} \left(\theta z + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right) f_{Z_E}(z) dz \\ &= \int_0^{\infty} A_k \sum_{n=0}^{T_k} B_k \sum_{n=0}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n z^n \frac{e^{z/ab}}{d} \times \left(\theta z + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right) \times \sqrt{\psi} A_k \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} B_k \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n m z^m \frac{e^{z/ab} (1/ab)}{d^2} \\ &\quad + \eta \sqrt{1 - \psi} dz. \end{aligned}$$

In order to solve above expression, we analyze (10) at high SNR. From (4), it follows that the dominating term is obtained for $n = 0$. Furthermore, using the approximation from [39] in (4), F_{Z_R} can be simplified as:

$$F_{Z_R} \left(\theta z + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right) = A_k^n B_k^n \lambda_k^n \frac{e^{z/ab}}{d}. \quad (24)$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_{11, \infty} &= A_k^n B_k^n \lambda_k^n \frac{e^{z/ab}}{d} \int_0^{\infty} \sqrt{\psi} A_k \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} B_k \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n m z^m \frac{e^{z/ab} (1/ab)}{d^2} \\ &\quad + \eta \sqrt{1 - \psi} dz. \end{aligned}$$

With the aid of [39, Eq. (7.621.4)], the above expression can be simplified as:

$$I_{11, \infty} = \left(B_R B_E \lambda_R^i \lambda_E^j \frac{e^{ab}}{d} \right) \times \sum_{n=0}^{L_R} C \theta^n \binom{L_R}{n} \frac{\theta - 1^{1-n}}{\psi_R \alpha}.$$

IV. SECRECY PERFORMANCE OVER EXPONENTIALLY CORRELATED NAKAGAMI- m FADING CHANNELS

In this section, we focus on the derivation of a received SNR to evaluate outage and secrecy performance of an mobile receiver over imperfect CSI. We assume that, the vehicle is at far distance from the node S . The exponentially correlated Nakagami- m channels are expressed in form of PDF as [36]:

$$c_{X \text{ Exp}}(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(S) b^S} x^{S-1} e^{-\frac{x}{b}}, \quad 0 \leq \rho < 1, \quad (25)$$

where $S = L + \frac{2\rho_1}{1-\rho_1} \left(L - \frac{1-\rho_1^L}{1-\rho_1} \right)$, L is number of branches, ρ_1 is exponential correlation coefficient. Under the vehicle mobility, the channel gain can be expressed as [37]:

$$h_X(t) = \frac{c_X(x)}{\sqrt{1 + d_x^\alpha}}, \quad (26)$$

where, α is the path loss component and $c_X(x)$ is the distribution of exponentially correlated Nakagami- m channel. The denominator term is relabeled as $c_Y(y)$ which is the distribution of distance. The PDF of vehicle mobility is expressed as [38]:

$$c_Y(y) = \frac{d}{2ab} \left(\arcsin\left(\frac{2(d^2 - d'^2)}{d^2} - 1\right) - \arcsin\left(\frac{2(d^2 - h^2)}{d^2} - 1\right) \right) \quad (27)$$

The CDF of received SNR can be given as :

$$C_Z(z) = \int_0^\infty \int_{-\infty}^{yz} c_{XY}(x, y) dx dy. \quad (28)$$

By substituting (25) and (27) in (28), the CDF can be written as:

$$C_Z(z) = \int_0^\infty \int_{-\infty}^{yz} \frac{1}{\Gamma(a) b^a} x^{a-1} e^{-\frac{x}{b}} \times \frac{d}{2ab} \left(\arcsin\left(\frac{2(d^2 - d'^2)}{d^2} - 1\right) - \arcsin\left(\frac{2(d^2 - h^2)}{d^2} - 1\right) \right) \quad (29)$$

By integrating (29) with the use of [39, Eq. (6.2)], we have a CDF for exponentially correlated Nakagami- m branches under vehicle mobility.

Lemma 4.1. *Under the impact of mobility, the CDF of received SNR for exponential correlation is obtained as the ratio of two distributions as:*

$$C_Z(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{T_k} E_k^n F_k^n \lambda_k^n z^m \frac{e^{z/ab}}{d} + \Gamma(m)(1 - m), \quad (30)$$

Corollary 4.1.1. *From the definition of PDF, by taking differentiation of (30), PDF for exponentially correlated Nakagami- m branches under vehicle mobility is expressed as (29). The differentiation terms is solved using the special integral rules of [41] and validated in MATHEMATICA.*

$$c_Z(z) = E_k F_k \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n m z^m \frac{e^{z/ab}(s/ab)}{d^2}. \quad (31)$$

Remark. *Finally from (1), the PDF of exponentially correlated Nakagami- m channels over imperfect CSI is expressed as:*

$$f_Z(z) = \sqrt{\psi} E_k F_k \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n m z^m \frac{e^{z/ab}(s/ab)}{d^2} + \eta \sqrt{1-\psi}. \quad (32)$$

A. Analysis of Outage Probability

Outage is stated as the probability that the received instantaneous SNR γ falls below a threshold γ_{th} . With the condition of outage probability as per (13), the outage probability for dual branch Nakagami- m over MRC in exponentially correlated fading channels can be written as:

$$P_{out} = \int_{z_{th}}^{\infty} c_Z(z) dz. \quad (33)$$

Substituting (32) in (33), the average probability of outage under vehicle mobility for a exponentially correlated Nakagami- m channels over imperfect CSI is expressed as:

$$P_{out} = \int_{z_{th}}^{\infty} \sqrt{\psi} E_k F_k \times \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n m z^m \frac{e^{z/ab}(1/ab)}{d^2} + \eta \sqrt{1-\psi} dz. \quad (34)$$

Expanding the inner series term and integrating (34), we have the closed form expression of average outage probability using special integrals in [39, Section 6.4]. The expression can be given as follows:

$$P_{out} = 1 - e^{ab/z_{th}} \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} \sum_{n=0}^m \Gamma(e^{\rho_1-1} + z^n) + (\psi^3/2e^{-d} + \eta^2) F_k + E_k. \quad (35)$$

Above equation is the outage probability under exponential correlation. where ρ_1 is the exponential correlation parameter.

B. Analysis of Secrecy Outage Probability

Similarly as performed in Section III, the secrecy outage probability under exponential correlation over Nakagami- m fading can be given as:

1) Derivation of Z_1

The inside integral term can be divided as per (18). The I_1 notation updated with Z_1 for the particular derivation. Hence the derivation of Z_{11} can be given as :

$$\begin{aligned} Z_{11} &= \int_0^\infty F_{Z_D} \left(\theta z + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right) f_{Z_E}(z) dz \\ &= \int_0^\infty A_k B_k \sum_{n=0}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n z^m \frac{e^{z/ab}}{d} \times \left(\theta z + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right) \times \sqrt{\psi} A_k B_k \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n m z^m \frac{e^{z/ab} (1/ab)}{d^2} + \eta \sqrt{1 - \psi} dz. \end{aligned}$$

Note that the above integral does not converge for any fixed value of z . However, the integral can be solved by taking an appropriate identity from [39, Section 8]. To reduce the complexity, we assume that the integral is limited. On rewriting, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} Z_{11} &= \int_0^\infty A_k B_k \sum_{n=0}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n z^m \frac{e^{z/ab}}{d} \times \left(\theta z + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right) \times \sqrt{\psi} A_k B_k \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n m z^m \frac{e^{z/ab} (1/ab)}{d^2} dz \\ &+ \int_0^\infty A_k B_k \sum_{n=0}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n z^m \frac{e^{z/ab}}{d} \times \left(\theta z + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right) \times \eta \sqrt{1 - \psi} dz. \end{aligned}$$

On further solving by using special integral forms in [40, Eq. 7.1.1], we obtain the following term as :

$$Z_{11} = A_R A_E \sum_{S_R} \sum_{S_E} \sum_{i=0}^{T_R} \sum_{j=1}^{T_E} \times \left(B_R B_E \lambda_R^i \lambda_E^j \frac{e^{ab}}{d} \right) \times \sum_{n=0}^{L_D} C \theta^n \binom{L_D}{n} \frac{\theta - 1^{1-n}}{\psi_D \alpha}, \quad (36)$$

Here $C = \left(L_E \Gamma \left(\frac{n+\psi}{\eta_D \theta} \right) + \rho \right)$, $A_R = \frac{2\rho_{1k}}{2d^2+1}$, $B_R = \frac{1}{L_m}$, $A_E = B_E = 1/m$

The analytical expression (34) states that SOP is affected by the exponential correlation among the antennas.

2) Derivation of Z_2

$$Z_2 \int_{I_p/P_{Max}}^\infty H(x) c_X(x) dx. \quad (37)$$

where $H(x) = \int_0^\infty C_{Y_R} (\theta y + (\theta - 1)) c_{Y_E}(y) dy$.

By solving above integral we have an additional term for the SOP. Here (29) is relabeled as C_{Y_R} and the PDF of it relabeled as c_{Y_E} .

$$Z_2 = E_k A_E \sum_{i=0}^{T_R} \sum_{i=0}^{T_E} (B_R B_E \lambda_R \lambda_E \theta^n x^{L_E}). \quad (38)$$

C. Asymptotic Analysis of Secrecy Outage Probability for Exponential Correlated Fading

From the expression of SOP in (20), we can notice that for the considered case, only integrals Z_{11} will be influenced. On rewriting I_1 , we have

$$\begin{aligned} Z_{11} &= \int_0^\infty F_{Z_D} \left(\theta z + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right) f_{Z_E}(z) dz \\ &= \int_0^\infty A_k B_k \sum_{n=0}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n z^m \frac{e^{z/ab}}{d} \times \left(\theta z + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right) \\ &\quad \times \sqrt{\psi} A_k B_k \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n m z^m \frac{e^{z/ab} (1/ab)}{d^2} + \eta \sqrt{1 - \psi} dz. \end{aligned}$$

In order to solve above expression, we analyze (29) at high SNR. From (29), it follows that the dominating term is obtained for $n = 0$. Furthermore, using the approximation from [39] in (20), F_{Z_R} can be simplified as:

$$F_{Z_R} \left(\theta z + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right) = E_k^n F_k^n \lambda_k^n z^m \frac{e^{z/ab}}{d} + \Gamma(m)(1 - m). \quad (39)$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_{11, \infty} &= E_k^n F_k^n \lambda_k^n z^m \frac{e^{z/ab}}{d} + \Gamma(m)(1 - m) \int_0^\infty \sqrt{\psi} A_k \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} B_k \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n m z^m \frac{e^{z/ab} (1/ab)}{d^2} \\ &\quad + \eta \sqrt{1 - \psi} dz. \end{aligned}$$

With the aid of [39, Eq. (7.622.2)], the above expression can be simplified as:

$$I_{11, \infty} = (A_R A_E \lambda_R \lambda_E \theta^n).$$

V. SECRECY PERFORMANCE OVER ARBITRARILY CORRELATED NAKAGAMI- m FADING CHANNELS

In this section, we focus on the derivation of a received SNR to evaluate the outage and secrecy performance of a mobile receiver over imperfect CSI. The arbitrarily correlated Nakagami- m channels are expressed in form of PDF as [36]:

$$g_X(x) = \frac{2x^{Lm-1}}{\Gamma(L)} \frac{m^{Lm}}{\Omega} \left(\frac{1}{\det(\Lambda)} \right)^m \times \Phi_2(m, m; Lm; \frac{mx^2}{\Omega}), \quad (40)$$

where $\Phi_2(\cdot)$ is the confluent Lauricella hyper geometric function related to L variables since we are dealing with dual branches the identity reduces to Φ_2 , $\det(\Lambda)$ is the correlation parameter (ρ) of the antenna branches calculated by [42], Ω denotes the $E[X^2]$ with arbitrarily powers, L denotes the number of branches. Consider the positive definite matrix which is also called as

correlation matrix with the elements of square roots of the power correlation coefficient. Eigen values of the correlation matrix are obtained from [42]. Under the vehicle mobility, the channel gain can be expressed as [37]

$$h_X(t) = \frac{g_X(x)}{\sqrt{1 + d_x^\alpha}}, \quad (41)$$

where α is the path loss component. The denominator term is relabeled as $g_Y(y)$ which is the distribution of distance. The PDF of vehicle mobility is expressed as [38]

$$g_Y(y) = \frac{d}{4ab} \left[\pi + 2\arcsin \left(\frac{2(y^2 - (b-s)^2)}{y^2} \right) - 1 \right]. \quad (42)$$

The CDF of received SNR can be given as

$$G_Z(z) = \int_0^\infty \int_{-\infty}^{yz} g_{XY}(x, y) dx dy. \quad (43)$$

By substituting (40) and (42) in (43), the CDF can be written as

$$G_Z(z) = \frac{2x^{Lm-1} m^{Lm}}{\Gamma(L) \Omega} \left(\frac{1}{\det(\Lambda)} \right)^m \times \Phi_2(m, m; Lm; \frac{mx^2}{\Omega}) \times \frac{d}{4ab} \left[\pi + 2\arcsin \left(\frac{2(y^2 - (b-s)^2)}{y^2} \right) - 1 \right]. \quad (44)$$

By integrating the equation (9), we have a CDF for uniformly correlated Nakagami- m branches under vehicle mobility.

Lemma 5.1. *Under the impact of mobility, the CDF of received SNR for arbitrarily correlation is obtained as the ratio of two distributions as:*

$$G_Z(z) = \frac{z^{2LmB_k}}{Lm} \times F_1(p, q; r; s) \times \frac{1}{\Gamma(m)} \left(\frac{m}{\Omega} \right)^{Lm} \times \frac{A_k}{\det(\Lambda)}^m, \quad (45)$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the Gamma function, where F_1 is monotonically decreasing generalized gaussian hyper geometric function of four terms given in [39, Section 4] where $p = \frac{z}{2abLm}$, $q = \frac{1-\det(\Lambda)}{4d}$, $r = \frac{2z}{2d^2+1}$, $s = \frac{1-\det(\Lambda)}{Lm}$, m is the Nakagami- m parameter.

For proof, kindly refer to Appendix A ■

Corollary 5.1.1. *From the definitions of PDF, by taking differentiation of (43) with the help of [39], PDF for uniformly correlated Nakagami- m branches under vehicle mobility is expressed as follows:*

$$g_Z(z) = \frac{\left(\frac{zm}{z}\right)^{d(Lm-1)} \exp\left(\frac{z}{z \times (1 - \det(\Lambda))}\right) \times A_k}{(1 - \det(\Lambda))^{d(L-1)} \Gamma(Lm)}. \quad (46)$$

Remark. Finally, the PDF of arbitrarily correlated Nakagami- m channels for imperfect CSI is expressed as:

$$g_Z(z) = \sqrt{\psi} \frac{\left(\frac{\gamma m}{\bar{\gamma}}\right)^{d(Lm-1)} \exp\left(\frac{-\gamma}{\bar{\gamma} \times (1 - \det(\Lambda))}\right) \times A_k}{(1 - \det(\Lambda))^{d(L-1)} \Gamma(Lm)} + \eta \sqrt{1 - \psi}. \quad (47)$$

where ψ is the imperfect channel state controlling parameter and η is the estimation error.

A. Analysis of Outage Probability

With the condition of outage probability as per (13), the outage probability for dual branch Nakagami- m over MRC in arbitrarily correlated fading channels as follows:

$$P_{out} = \int_{z_{th}}^{\infty} g_Z(z) dz \quad (48)$$

Substituting (12) in (48), the average probability of outage under vehicle mobility for an arbitrarily correlated Nakagami- m channels over imperfect CSI is expressed as:

$$P_{out} = \int_{z_{th}}^{\infty} \sqrt{\psi} \frac{\left(\frac{\gamma m}{\bar{\gamma}}\right)^{d(Lm-1)} \exp\left(\frac{-\gamma}{\bar{\gamma} \times (1 - \det(\Lambda))}\right) \times A_k}{(1 - \det(\Lambda))^{d(L-1)} \Gamma(Lm)} + \eta \sqrt{1 - \psi} dz. \quad (49)$$

Integrating (49), we have the closed form expression of average outage probability using special integrals in [39, Section 6]. The expression can be written as:

$$P_{out} = 1 - e^{ab/z_{th}} \sum_1^{T_k} \sum_{n=0}^m \Gamma(e^r - 1 + z) + (\psi^3/2e^{-d} + \eta^2) A_k + \binom{N}{L} B_k + A_k \psi \Gamma(\det \Lambda)^m. \quad (50)$$

Above equation is the outage probability under the arbitrarily correlation.

B. Analysis of Secrecy Outage Probability

1) Derivation of U_1

The inside integral can be divided as per (18). The I_1 notation updated with U_1 for the particular derivation. The derivation of U_{11} can be given as :

$$\begin{aligned}
U_{11} &= \int_0^\infty F_{Z_D} \left(\theta z + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right) f_{Z_E}(z) dz \\
&= \int_0^\infty \frac{z^{2LmB_k}}{Lm} \times F_1(p, q; r; s) \frac{1}{\Gamma(m)} \left(\frac{m}{\Omega} \right)^{Lm} \times \frac{A_k}{\det(\Lambda)}^m \sqrt{\psi} \frac{\left(\frac{\gamma m}{\gamma} \right)^{d(Lm-1)} \exp\left(\frac{-\gamma}{\gamma \times (1 - \det(\Lambda))} \right) \times A_k}{(1 - \det(\Lambda))^{d(L-1)} \Gamma(Lm)} \\
&\quad + \eta \sqrt{1 - \psi} dz.
\end{aligned}$$

Note that the above integral does not converge for any fixed value of z . However, the integral can be solved by taking an appropriate identity from [39, Section 4]. To reduce the complexity we assume that the integral is limited. On rewriting, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
U_{11} &= \int_0^\infty \frac{z^{2LmB_k}}{Lm} \times F_1(p, q; r; s) \frac{1}{\Gamma(m)} \left(\frac{m}{\Omega} \right)^{Lm} \times \frac{A_k}{\det(\Lambda)}^m dz \\
&\quad + \times \sqrt{\psi} \frac{\left(\frac{\gamma m}{\gamma} \right)^{d(Lm-1)} \exp\left(\frac{-\gamma}{\gamma \times (1 - \det(\Lambda))} \right) \times A_k}{(1 - \det(\Lambda))^{d(L-1)} \Gamma(Lm)} \eta \sqrt{1 - \psi} dz.
\end{aligned}$$

By keeping constant outside of the integral and further solving by using special integral forms in [40, Eq. 3.11], we obtained the following term

$$U_{11} = A_R A_E \sum_{S_R} \sum_{S_E} \sum_{i=0}^{T_R} \sum_{j=1}^{T_E} \times \left(B_R B_E \lambda_R^i \lambda_E^j \frac{e^{ab}}{d} \right) \times \sum_{n=0}^{L_D} C \theta^n \binom{L_D}{n} \frac{\theta - 1^{1-n}}{\psi_D \alpha}, \quad (51)$$

Here $C = \left(L_E \Gamma\left(\frac{n+\psi}{\eta_D \theta}\right) + \Lambda_k \right)$, $A_R = \frac{2}{2d^2+1}$, $B_R = \frac{1}{Lm}$, $A_E = B_E = 1/m$

Note that the SOP of legitimate receiver depends upon its channel conditions and as well as the number of antennas at eavesdropper side. The analytical expression (53) states that SOP is affected by the arbitrarily correlation among the antennas.

2) Derivation of U_2

When the $P_S = \frac{I_P}{X}$, by using (19), we can obtain :

$$U_2 = \int_{I_P/P_{Max}}^\infty H(x) g_X(x) dx. \quad (52)$$

where $H(x) = \int_0^\infty G_{Y_D}(\theta y + (\theta - 1)) g_{Y_E}(y) dy$

$$U_2 = A_R F_K \sum_{i=0}^{T_R} \sum_{i=0}^{T_E} (B_R B_E \lambda_R \lambda_E \theta^n x^{L_E}). \quad (53)$$

Kindly refer to Appendix A ■

C. Asymptotic Analysis of Secrecy Outage Probability over Arbitrarily Correlated Fading

From the expression of SOP in (20), we can notice that for the considered case, only integrals U_{11} will be influenced. On rewriting I_1 , we have

$$\begin{aligned} U_{11} &= \int_0^\infty F_{Z_D} \left(\theta z + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right) f_{Z_E}(z) dz \\ &= \int_0^\infty \frac{z^{2LmB_k}}{Lm} \times F_1(p, q; r; s) \frac{1}{\Gamma(m)} \left(\frac{m}{\Omega} \right)^{Lm} \times \frac{A_k}{\det(\Lambda)}^m \sqrt{\psi} \frac{\left(\frac{\gamma m}{\bar{\gamma}} \right)^{d(Lm-1)} \exp\left(\frac{-\gamma}{\bar{\gamma} \times (1 - \det(\Lambda))} \right)}{(1 - \det(\Lambda))^{d(L-1)} \Gamma(Lm)} \times A_k \\ &\quad + \eta \sqrt{1 - \psi} dz. \end{aligned}$$

In order to solve above expression, we analyze (43) at high SNR. From (43), it follows that the dominating term is obtained for $n = 0$. Furthermore, using the approximation from [39] in (20), F_{Z_R} can be simplified as:

$$F_{Z_R} \left(\theta z + \frac{\theta - 1}{\alpha} \right) = F_1(p, q; r; s) \frac{1}{\Gamma(m)} \left(\frac{m}{\Omega} \right)^{Lm} \times \frac{A_k}{\det(\Lambda)}^m. \quad (54)$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_{11, \infty} &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(m)} \left(\frac{m}{\Omega} \right)^{Lm} \times \frac{A_k}{\det(\Lambda)}^m \int_0^\infty \sqrt{\psi} A_k \sum B_k \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n m z^m \frac{e^{z/ab} (1/ab)}{d^2} \\ &\quad + \eta \sqrt{1 - \psi} dz. \end{aligned}$$

With the aid of [39, Eq. (7.622.2)], the above expression can be simplified as:

$$I_{11, \infty} = \left(B_R B_E \lambda_R^i \lambda_E^j \frac{e^{ab}}{d} \right) \times \sum_{n=0}^{L_D} C \theta^n \binom{L_D}{n} \frac{\theta - 1^{1-n}}{\psi_D \alpha},$$

$$A_R = \frac{2}{2d^2+1} \quad B_R = \frac{1}{Lm}, \quad A_E = B_E = 1/m$$

VI. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the average outage probability and secrecy outage probability for uniform, exponential, and arbitrary correlation effect are discussed and analyzed. This section demonstrates the effect of mobility on outage and secrecy outage probability. The vehicular scenario is considered in which antenna correlation under the imperfect channel state is also evaluated. Moreover, the outage performance for the shaping parameter is also evaluated. In highly correlated scenario, often the outage is higher which implies that the spacing between the antennas placed on a mobile vehicle can significantly contribute to the outage performance of the system performance. In general, the system is having better outage probably can withstand over eavesdropping smoothly because, at the eavesdropper side, it is difficult to achieve the information rate that overcomes the rate of legitimate link. In this case, how the correlation at the eavesdropper side behaves

TABLE I: Simulation Parameters

Sr.No	Parameters	Value
1	Carrier frequency (f_c)	1.9 GHz
2	Signal-to-noise ratio ($\overline{\gamma E}$)	12 dB
3	Code rate (R_s)	9.6 kbps
4	Path loss component (α)	0.9
5	Fading parameter (m)	1 & 4
6	Road width (b)	30m
7	Road length (a)	2 km
8	PU distance from road (d'')	400m
9	PU protection range (R')	1 km

is also evaluated at lower rate. Simulations are carried out to demonstrate the accuracy of our derived analytical expressions. Based on the parameters given in Table 1, we also plot the analytical expressions for the outage probability, and secrecy outage probability derived in Section III, IV, and V for uniform, exponential and arbitrary correlation respectively. These parameters are responsible to satisfy the requirement of urban scenario in which the speed limit can be up to 40km/h. The motivation behind this is to analyse the secrecy performance for the urban case in which the legitimate receiver as well as eavesdropper is moving with the constant speed. According to the scenario, we have also considered the path loss effect. Here, the objective is to identify that for example $v=0$ (Static condition + uncorrelated antennas), $v=15$, exponential (Receiver is moving at the velocity of 15km/h and having spacing between the equipped antennas), $v=15$, uniform (Receiver is moving at the velocity of 15km/h and having closely spaced equipped antennas), how the secrecy performance is varied. The results mainly indicate the effect of correlation over imperfect CSI on the outage probability and secrecy outage probability for considered urban vehicular networks. Here the line and marker illustrate the analytical and simulation results respectively.

A. Simulation Results for Cognitive Vehicular Networks

Fig. 2 demonstrates the outage performance for uniform and exponential correlation under the vehicle at 15km/h with the partially perfect channel condition 0.6. The effect of antenna correlation with these fixed channel conditions is tested under the various vehicle mobility. The antenna correlation should be exponentially correlated instead of a uniform and arbitrary to achieve better outage for any vehicle speed. Here up to the average SNR of 10 dB under vehicle mobility, we can observe the no fluctuations in the outage, which means the minimum requirement of SNR at any particular mobility should be 10 dB. The outage gets better at the

Fig. 2: Outage probability against received SNR for uniform and exponential correlations ($m = 4, d' = 100\text{m}, a = 2 \text{ km}, b = 30\text{m}, \psi = 1$) Fig. 3: outage probability against received SNR for arbitrary correlation ($m = 4, d' = 100\text{m}, a = 2 \text{ km}, b = 30\text{m}, \psi = 1$)

Fig. 4: Outage probability against correlation coefficient ($m = 4, d' = 100\text{m}, a = 2 \text{ km}, b = 30\text{m}, \psi = 1$) Fig. 5: Average outage probability against correlation coefficient ($m = 4, d' = 100\text{m}, a = 2 \text{ km}, b = 30\text{m}, \psi = 1$)

25 dB. Here, our approach is to restrict the velocity up to the 25 km/h for all numerical results, which is usual in dense traffic scenarios.

Fig. 3 represents the outage performance for arbitrary correlation under various velocity considering a low and high speed of eavesdropper. The correlation coefficient is plotted to

Fig. 6: Secrecy Outage probability against secrecy rate ($m = 4$, $d' = 100\text{m}$, $a = 2 \text{ km}$, $b = 30\text{m}$, $\psi = 1$)

Fig. 7: Outage probability against secrecy rate ($m = 4$, $d' = 100\text{m}$, $a = 2 \text{ km}$, $b = 30\text{m}$, $\psi = 1$)

Fig. 8: Secrecy outage probability against interference power for uniform correlation ($m = 4$, $d' = 100\text{m}$, $a = 2 \text{ km}$, $b = 30\text{m}$, $\psi = 1$)

Fig. 9: Secrecy outage probability against interference power for exponential correlation ($m = 4$, $d' = 100\text{m}$, $a = 2 \text{ km}$, $b = 30\text{m}$, $\psi = 1$)

demonstrate the spacing requirement between the antennas to achieve outage as low as possible. It is shown that at low SNR and high velocity, even a low correlation can cause a higher outage. In that case, channel conditions can play a vital role in achieving lower outage. In this case, we have assumed that the channel is imperfect. The secrecy performance is vulnerable to the fading

Fig. 10: Secrecy outage probability against interference power for arbitrary correlation ($m = 4$, $d' = 100\text{m}$, $a = 2 \text{ km}$, $b = 30\text{m}$, $\psi = 1$)

Fig. 11: SOP against shape parameter ($m = 4$, $d' = 100\text{m}$, $a = 2 \text{ km}$, $b = 30\text{m}$, $\psi = 1$)

scenarios and its magnitude and value of shape parameter.

The more realistic imperfect channel condition is considered to be evaluated for the correlation coefficient under vehicle mobility in Fig. 4. From the outage performance in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 over perfect channel, the clear upper bound of a correlation coefficient is obtained for various velocity. The correlation having greater than 0.2 under the imperfect channel can demolish the system outage performance. Moreover, if the imperfect channel parameter is reduced to 0.6, the effect of correlation on the outage performance can be compensated as per Fig. 5. From Fig. 6, the average secrecy outage performance is evaluated at the eavesdropper side; based on that,

Fig. 12: ASOP against interference power ($m = 4$, $d' = 100\text{m}$, $a = 2 \text{ km}$, $b = 30\text{m}$, $\psi = 1$)

the secrecy performance at a special rate at eavesdropper is assessed for different two values of velocity. Here, we are not assuming any fixed data rate at the receiver side in order to give the justification for perfect secrecy. It can be noticed that secrecy outage is higher for uniform correlation at any fixed velocity and secrecy rate. The result shows the impact of data rate at the eavesdropper side for improving the secrecy outage performance. It can be noticed that the for any value of fixed velocity, the need for a secrecy rate obtained for uniform correlation varies with the interference power. Under the imperfect channel estimation, the result is obtained to evaluate the average of SOP, which implies that whatever the secrecy rate is obtained at the eavesdropper side, there should be some minimum secrecy outage if the interference power from the primary user side is comparatively low.

Fig. 7 demonstrates the outage probability obtained under the specific rate at the eavesdropper side. The secrecy outage is obtained for partially imperfect channel condition parameter 0.6. However, the secrecy is not obtained for the imperfect channel conditions even for a low rate.

Fig. 8 demonstrates the impact of uniform correlation for various velocity with respect to the interference power. It shows the impact of spacing between the antennas on secrecy performance. Antennas which are closely spaced at the legitimate receiver may turn in to high outage at the various speed which implies that the similarity between received multi path component is higher. Fig. 9 demonstrates the effect of exponential correlation concerning various velocity under the perfect channel estimation. The antennas which are not closely spaced at the legitimate receiver side pay a significant outage at a different speed but less than the uniform correlation, which will be highlighted as an error analysis in further discussions. Fig. 10 demonstrates the impact

of arbitrary association for various velocity under the perfect channel estimation. The antennas which are not closely spaced in a linear array at the legitimate receiver side, pay a significant outage at various velocities. It can be noticed that, for all correlation schemes, the correlation at eavesdropper's (ρ_e) channels outperforms the loss on legitimate receiver's channel. Though, the improvement on the secrecy performance is also dependent on the vehicle velocity. Moreover, it can be noticed that the high vehicle velocity turns in the higher secrecy outage implies that at the higher velocity the V2I link is experiencing the effect of Doppler effect as well as the fading which reduces its strength and therefore the privacy of the system compromised. Moreover, when the antenna correlation is considered with the effect of mobility, the secrecy performance further compromised. It can be also noticed that while varying the velocity and the antenna correlation we assume the constant secrecy rate. If the secrecy rate is also varies the results may get change. The secrecy outage against the shape parameter is plotted in Fig. 11, the result clearly shows that the Raleigh fading case ($m = 1$), outage at uniform correlation is highest. The dynamic fading scenario ($m = 4$), performs better under perfect CSI. Moreover, Fig. 11 also shows the comparison among the different correlation type between antennas. The advantage of using dynamic Nakagami- m fading in comparison to Rayleigh is indicated. The average outage is evaluated under the fixed velocity of 25 km/h, and It can be shown that the uniform and arbitrary correlation performs poorly than the exponential correlation. However, at a particular decorrelation distance at which the antennas are assumed as independent, the outage performance improves. The arbitrary correlation can be taken as a special case of uniform correlation in which the correlation matrix was having all the constant equal values. Note that the SOP is also dependent upon the velocity of a legitimate receiver and eavesdropper. For the unequal velocity of both the nodes, it is quite challenging to achieve the perfect secrecy and Fig. 12 illustrates the average of secrecy outage over uniform correlation. Fig. 13 and Fig. 14, represents the asymptotic behavior of SOP and OP respectively. The SNR at the eavesdropper side kept constant while increase the SNR at the legitimate receiver side. The result demonstrates that at the high SNR, the exponential correlated fading performs better than any other.

B. Inferences from the simulations:

We explain the effect of each parameter on the secrecy performance as below:

- 1) Impact of high fading parameters : The high fading parameter value ($m = 4$) often reduces to the dynamic fading which is more realistic for the vehicular scenario. The behavior of the outage probability at high fading parameter varies rapidly with the variation in velocity. Therefore, it is expected that the secrecy performance is affected due to high velocity but the impact of this degradation is accountable and can be overcome easily by considering

Fig. 13: Asymptotic Behavior of Secrecy Outage Probability ($m = 4$, $d' = 100m$, $a = 2$ km, $b = 30m$, $\psi = 1$, $v = 25$ km/h) Fig. 14: Asymptotic Behavior of Outage Probability ($m = 4$, $d' = 100m$, $a = 2$ km, $b = 30m$, $\psi = 1$, $v = 25$ km/h, $I_p = 2$ dB)

5

Fig. 15: Outage Probability vs. SNR with MRC over i.n.i.d and i.i.d 5channel for $m = 1$.

$m = 4$. Now the matter is to check the secrecy performance for the values of $m \geq 4$, which turned up into the line of sight communication is more effective to establish a communication link. Now when we observe the analytical expressions at $m \geq 4$ has much better outage and secrecy outage probability. From this observation we can conclude that the consideration of high fading parameter can improves the secrecy performance subjected to the constant relative velocity and SNR. Thus how we can analyse the impact of high fading with lower complexity on secrecy performance.

- 2) Impact of considering dual antennas : This is fact that the higher number of antennas greater than 1 at the receiver side would lies in the receiver diversity. The signal reconstruction by performing the receiver diversity can have an accurate approximations to the original transmitted signal. Thus, by considering the higher number of antennas will directly affects the signal quality after processing. Now, If we observe the analytical expressions of the outage probability, the performance is significantly improves for higher antennas in comparison with single branches. Provided with the fact that we are having the highly dynamic fading scenario ($m > 4$ and higher), the outage can be achieved even better by keeping constant the velocity and SNR. Thus, we observe the improvement in secrecy performance with the higher number of antennas.

- 3) Impact of correlated channels : As we can notice that the spacing between the antennas turns into the various correlations. In the considered network model, we have considered the antenna correlation at both legitimate receiver side, and eavesdropper side. Depending on the type of the correlation at the legitimate receiver side, the behaviour of secrecy performance can be changed. The findings suggest that exponentially correlated antenna at the receiver side and uniformly correlated at the eavesdropper side is an advantageous combination to have.

C. Computation time and Accuracy Analysis

In the following, the computation time and the accuracy analysis of our proposed analytical expressions are discussed for the considered over correlated Nakagami- m channels. To facilitate

TABLE II: Computation Time

	Fig. 2	Fig. 3	Fig. 4	Fig. 5	Fig. 6	Fig. 7	Fig. 8	Fig. 9	Fig. 10	Fig. 11	Fig. 12
Simulation	1150	240	2340	230	3218	3250	448	470	275	448	338
Analysis	2.32	1.21	32.8	11.7	34.8	27.6	21	19.8	13.8	17.6	6.89
Platform: Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-4790 CPU @ 3.60 GHz, Memory : 8 GB											Unit: s

the accuracy analysis, we illustrate the error analysis for Fig. 8, 9, and 10. We calculate the error by subtracting the simulation result value and analytical result value and dividing it from the simulated result value. Moreover, the computational time in Fig. 5, 6, 7, and 9 are mostly due to the comparison point of view between the correlation schemes. The computational error (in percentage) is carried out for the low velocity at 2 km/h of an eavesdropper, which significantly depends on the correlation type (higher for arbitrary correlation) as it can be noticed from Table V and which are quite suitable in practical scenarios.

TABLE III: Computation error for Fig. 8

$\rho \backslash I_p$	5	10	15	20	25
0	2.61	1.528	4.09	0.14	3.62
0.5	3.456	2.4	9.90	0.01	2.92
0.9	3.38	2.36	4.25	0.23	0.05

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we investigate the secrecy outage probability and average outage probability to secure communications over correlated Nakagami- m channel assuming MRC for vehicular

TABLE IV: Computation error for Fig. 9

$\rho \backslash I_p$	5	10	15	20	25
0	4.11	3.428	1.09	1.56	5.12
0.5	2.15	1.4	5.90	3.01	4.12
0.9	2.18	1.26	3.15	1.25	1.65

TABLE V: Computation error for Fig. 10

$\rho \backslash I_p$	5	10	15	20	25
0	7.61	4.31	3.19	2.43	4.79
0.5	4.16	3.42	3.90	2.01	2.62
0.9	2.83	4.61	4.25	4.53	3.05

communications. The various antenna correlations like a uniform, exponential and arbitrary are being considered. We observe that under the impact of velocity, it is better to have some distance (less than the decorrelation) between the antennas under the dynamic fading conditions. However, the same performance can be degraded under the imperfectness of the channel. The exact closed-form expressions for average outage and secrecy outage have been derived. Moreover, error analysis is carried out. Simulation validates the accuracy of analytical expressions. The obtained results show the impact of various correlation types among the antennas on secrecy performance. We also observed the joint impact of antenna correlation and imperfect channel condition on the outage and secrecy outage probability which reflects that it is advantageous to have exponentially correlated branches at the legitimate receiver side and uniformly correlated branches at the eavesdropper side.

APPENDIX A PROOF OF LEMMAS

In order to evaluate the secrecy outage probability over arbitrary correlation, the received SNR under the vehicle mobility can be derived by calculating the CDFs which is given as:

$$F_Z(z) = \int_0^\infty \int_{-\infty}^{yz} f_{XY}(x, y) dx dy \quad (55)$$

Since both the distributions are independent from each other and by substituting (3) and (4) in (13) we have,

$$F_Z(z) = \int_0^\infty \int_{-\infty}^{yz} \frac{2x^{Lm-1}}{\Gamma(L)} \frac{m^{Lm}}{\Omega} \left(\frac{1}{\det(\Lambda)} \right)^m \times \Phi_2(m, m; Lm; \frac{mx^2}{\Omega}) \times f_Y(y) dx dy \quad (56)$$

At first integrating the inner integral with respect to dx and from [39, Eq. 6.4.1] the integral in (14) is further given by considering the appropriate identities

$$F_Z(z) = \frac{z^2}{ab} \times \frac{1}{\Gamma(m)} \times \left(\frac{1}{\det(\Lambda)} \right)^m \times \int_0^\infty y \operatorname{Arcsin} \left(2y^2 - \frac{(b-h)^2}{y^2} \right) y^2 F_1(\cdot) dy \quad (57)$$

Further to obtain final CDF, integrating again the above equation with respect to dy , by rearranging constant terms and performing some steps (58) is further given as:

$$F_Z(z) = \frac{yz^{Lm}}{Lm} \left[\frac{2\Gamma(-0.5+m)\Gamma(Lm)}{2\Gamma(m)\Gamma(m)} \right] \times \int_0^\infty y \operatorname{Arcsin} \left(2y^2 - \frac{(b-h)^2}{y^2} \right) y^2 F_1(\cdot) dy + yz F_1(\cdot) \int_0^\infty y \operatorname{Arcsin} \left(2y^2 - \frac{(b-h)^2}{y^2} \right) y^2 F_1(\cdot) dy \quad (58)$$

Using [39, Section 6] and solving the integral by performing necessary steps, (59) is further simplified as given in (44). where, $F_1 = [\{0.5, m, m\}, \{1.5, Lm\}, yz^2]$. CDF can be expressed as:

$$G_Z(z) = \frac{z^{2LmB_k}}{Lm} \times F_1(p, q; r; s) \times \frac{1}{\Gamma(m)} \left(\frac{m}{\Omega} \right)^{Lm} \times \frac{A_k}{\det(\Lambda)} \quad (59)$$

where, $p = \frac{z}{2abLm}$, $q = \frac{1-\det(\Lambda)}{4d}$, $r = \frac{2z}{2d^2+1}$, $s = \frac{1-\det(\Lambda)}{Lm}$, $T_k = m_k L$ and $\lambda_k = e^{T_k}$

By differentiating the above equation we get the PDFs of received SNR under arbitrary correlation which is further used to evaluate the outage probability. Similarly, we get for the exponential and uniform correlation. Furthermore by utilising the PDFs, the inner integrals to evaluate the SOP,

$$I_2 = \int_{I_p/P_{Max}}^\infty H(x) f_X(x) dx \quad (60)$$

where $H(x) = \int_0^\infty F_{Y_D}(\theta y + (\theta - 1)) f_{Y_E}(y) dy$

By substituting the respective PDF and CDF of the effective fading condition over different correlation schemes and solving the integral, we the second term for the secrecy outage probability. Here the calculation is provided over the uniform correlation.

$$I_2 = A_k B_k \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n m z^m \frac{e^{z/ab} (1/ab)}{d^2} \times \sqrt{\psi} \times A_k B_k \sum_{n=1}^{T_k} \lambda_k^n m z^m \frac{e^{z/ab} (1/ab)}{d^2} + \eta \sqrt{1-\psi} \quad (61)$$

The above equation formed a general expression of reduced identity by performing Lagrangian polynomial for n term given in [39, Section 4, 6, 8]. At last, we get the reduced term as (21). Similarly, by substituting a respective PDFs and CDFs for exponential and arbitrarily correlation, we get the another reduced term for the same.

REFERENCES

- [1] X. Zhou, L. Song, and Y. Zhang, *Physical Layer Security in Wireless Communications*. CRC Press, 2013.
- [2] J. Barros and M. R. D. Rodrigues, "Secrecy capacity of wireless channels," in *Proc. IEEE International Symposium on Information Theory*, July 2006, pp. 356–360.
- [3] C. E. Shannon, "Communication theory of secrecy systems," *Bell system technical journal*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 656–715, 1949.
- [4] Y.-S. Shiu, S. Y. Chang, H.-C. Wu, S. C.-H. Huang, and H.-H. Chen, "Physical layer security in wireless networks: A tutorial," *IEEE wireless Commun.*, vol. 18, no. 2, 2011.
- [5] A. D. Wyner, "The wire-tap channel," *Bell system technical journal*, vol. 54, no. 8, pp. 1355–1387, 1975.
- [6] S. Goel and R. Negi, "Guaranteeing secrecy using artificial noise," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 2180–2189, June 2008.
- [7] P. Papadimitratos, A. D. L. Fortelle, K. Evenssen, R. Brignolo, and S. Cosenza, "Vehicular communication systems: Enabling technologies, applications, and future outlook on intelligent transportation," *IEEE Commun. Mag.*, vol. 47, no. 11, pp. 84–95, November 2009.
- [8] J. Eze, S. Zhang, E. Liu, and E. Eze, "Cognitive radio-enabled internet of vehicles: a cooperative spectrum sensing and allocation for vehicular communication," *IET Networks*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 190–199, 2018.
- [9] Z. Shu, Y. Qian, and S. Ci, "On physical layer security for cognitive radio networks," *IEEE Netw.*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 28–33, 2013.
- [10] I. Csiszár and J. Körner, "Broadcast channels with confidential messages," *IEEE Trans. Info. Theory*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 339–348, 1978.
- [11] A. Khisti and G. W. Wornell, "Secure transmission with multiple antennas i: The misome wiretap channel," *IEEE Trans. Info. Theory*, vol. 56, no. 7, pp. 3088–3104, 2010.
- [12] R. Zhang and Y.-C. Liang, "Exploiting multi-antennas for opportunistic spectrum sharing in cognitive radio networks," *IEEE J. Sel. Topics Signal Process.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 88–102, 2008.
- [13] N. S. Ferdinand, D. B. da Costa, and M. Latva-aho, "Effects of outdated CSI on the secrecy performance of miso wiretap channels with transmit antenna selection," *IEEE Commun. Lett.*, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 864–867, May 2013.
- [14] H. Lei, H. Zhang, I. S. Ansari, C. Gao, Y. Guo, G. Pan, and K. A. Qaraqe, "Secrecy outage performance for SIMO underlay cognitive radio systems with generalized selection combining over nakagami- m channels," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 65, no. 12, pp. 10126–10132, Dec 2016.
- [15] H. Lei, C. Gao, I. S. Ansari, Y. Guo, Y. Zou, G. Pan, and K. A. Qaraqe, "Secrecy outage performance of transmit antenna selection for mimo underlay cognitive radio systems over nakagami- m channels," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 66, no. 3, pp. 2237–2250, March 2017.
- [16] W. A. Al-Hussaini and F. H. Ali, "A closed-form approximation of correlated multiuser mimo ergodic capacity with antenna selection and imperfect channel estimation," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 67, no. 6, pp. 5515–5519, June 2018.
- [17] Y. Ai, M. Cheffena, A. Mathur, and H. Lei, "On physical layer security of double rayleigh fading channels for vehicular communications," *IEEE Wireless Commun. Lett.*, pp. 1–1, 2018.
- [18] G. Pan, C. Tang, X. Zhang, T. Li, Y. Weng, and Y. Chen, "Physical-layer security over non-small-scale fading channels," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 65, no. 3, pp. 1326–1339, March 2016.
- [19] X. Jiang, C. Zhong, X. Chen, T. Q. Duong, T. A. Tsiftsis, and Z. Zhang, "Secrecy performance of wirelessly powered wiretap channels," *IEEE Trans. Commun.*, vol. 64, no. 9, pp. 3858–3871, Sept 2016.
- [20] P. Parada and R. Blahut, "Secrecy capacity of SIMO and slow fading channels," in *Proc. of IEEE International Symposium on Information Theory*, 2005, pp. 2152–2155.
- [21] K. Lee, J. Lim, and H. Choi, "Impact of Outdated CSI on the Secrecy Performance of Wireless-Powered Untrusted Relay Networks," *IEEE Trans. Inf. Forensics Security*, vol. 15, pp. 1423–1433, 2020.

- [22] Y.-W. P. Hong, P.-C. Lan, and C.-C. J. Kuo, "Enhancing physical-layer secrecy in multiantenna wireless systems: An overview of signal processing approaches," *IEEE Signal Process. Mag.*, vol. 30, no. 5, pp. 29–40, 2013.
- [23] H. Lei, C. Gao, I. S. Ansari, Y. Guo, G. Pan, and K. A. Qaraqe, "On physical-layer security over simo generalized- k fading channels," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 65, no. 9, pp. 7780–7785, 2016.
- [24] L. Liang, H. Peng, G. Y. Li, and X. Shen, "Vehicular communications: A physical layer perspective," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 66, no. 12, pp. 10 647–10 659, 2017.
- [25] L. Zhang, R. Zhang, Y.-C. Liang, Y. Xin, and S. Cui, "On the relationship between the multi-antenna secrecy communications and cognitive radio communications," *IEEE Trans. Commun.*, vol. 58, no. 6, pp. 1877–1886, 2010.
- [26] J. Tang, M. Dabaghchian, K. Zeng, and H. Wen, "Impact of mobility on physical layer security over wireless fading channels," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 17, no. 12, pp. 7849–7864, 2018.
- [27] A. U. Makarfi, K. M. Rabie, O. Kaiwartya, X. Li, and R. Kharel, "Physical Layer Security in Vehicular Networks with Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces," in *Proc. of 91st Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC2020-Spring)*, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [28] L. Xu, X. Yu, H. Wang, X. Dong, Y. Liu, W. Lin, X. Wang, and J. Wang, "Physical layer security performance of mobile vehicular networks," *Mobile Networks and Applications*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 643–649, 2020.
- [29] B. Ji, Y. Li, D. Cao, C. Li, S. Mumtaz, and D. Wang, "Secrecy Performance Analysis of UAV Assisted Relay Transmission for Cognitive Network With Energy Harvesting," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 69, no. 7, pp. 7404–7415, 2020.
- [30] J. Sun, H. Bie, X. Li, J. Zhang, G. Pan, and K. M. Rabie, "Secrecy Performance Analysis of SIMO Systems Over Correlated $\kappa - \mu$ Shadowed Fading Channels," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 86 090–86 101, 2019.
- [31] J. Tang, G. Chen, and J. P. Coon, "Secrecy Performance Analysis of Wireless Communications in the Presence of UAV Jammer and Randomly Located UAV Eavesdroppers," *IEEE Trans. Inf. Forensics Security*, vol. 14, no. 11, pp. 3026–3041, 2019.
- [32] L. Yang, Y. Jinxia, W. Xie, M. Hasna, T. Tsiftsis, and M. Di Renzo, "Secrecy Performance Analysis of RIS-Aided Wireless Communication Systems," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, pp. 1–1, 2020.
- [33] A. Mathur, Y. Ai, M. Cheffena, and G. Kaddoum, "Secrecy Performance of Correlated $\alpha - \mu$ Fading Channels," *IEEE Commun. Lett.*, vol. 23, no. 8, pp. 1323–1327, 2019.
- [34] Y. Li, K. An, T. Liang, and X. Yan, "Secrecy Performance of Land Mobile Satellite Systems With Imperfect Channel Estimation and Multiple Eavesdroppers," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 31 751–31 761, 2019.
- [35] L. Gahane, P. K. Sharma, N. Varshney, T. A. Tsiftsis, and P. Kumar, "An improved energy detector for mobile cognitive users over generalized fading channels," *IEEE Trans. Commun.*, vol. 66, no. 2, pp. 534–545, Feb 2018.
- [36] V. A. Aalo, "Performance of maximal-ratio diversity systems in a correlated nakagami-fading environment," *IEEE Trans. Commun.*, vol. 43, no. 8, pp. 2360–2369, 1995.
- [37] Y. Ai, M. Cheffena, A. Mathur, and H. Lei, "On physical layer security of double rayleigh fading channels for vehicular communications," *IEEE Commun Lett.*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 1038–1041, Dec 2018.
- [38] S. Zhu, C. Guo, C. Feng, and X. Liu, "Performance analysis of cooperative spectrum sensing in cognitive vehicular networks with dense traffic," in *Proc. VTC Spring*, 2016, pp. 1–6.
- [39] I. S. Gradshteyn and I. M. Ryzhik, *Table of integrals, series, and products*. Academic press, 2014.
- [40] M. Abramowitz and I. Stegun, "Handbook of mathematical functions with formulas, graphs, and mathematical tables (u.s. department of commerce, washington, dc,)," 10 2018.
- [41] A. D. Rich and D. J. Jeffrey, "A knowledge repository for indefinite integration based on transformation rules," in *International Conference on Intelligent Computer Mathematics*. Springer, 2009, pp. 480–485.
- [42] M. Z. Win, G. Chrisikos, and J. H. Winters, "MRC performance for M-ary modulation in arbitrarily correlated nakagami fading channels," *IEEE Commun. Lett.*, vol. 4, no. 10, pp. 301–303, 2000.